

Cluster and Conquer: The Use of Clustering-Triggered Emission Materials in Photodynamic Therapy

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Abstract

Today, there is no doubt that light is transforming modern medicine and healthcare through its ability to accurately diagnose and treat disease in complex biological systems facilitated by a wide range of luminescent agents and imaging techniques. Although there are inevitable limitations, including biocompatibility issues, the ability to tune spectral properties, and the ease and affordability of synthesis, circumventing aggregation-induced quenching at high concentrations or in aqueous physiological conditions remains a significant challenge. In this context, Clustering-Triggered Emission (CTE), in which atomic cluster formation induces light absorption and the luminescence of unconventional chromophores, offers an all-in-one solution to all the identified challenges. If the luminescent properties of CTE materials include attributes once thought to be exclusive to conventional chromophores, it seems reasonable that new capabilities, such as the formation of highly oxidative reactive oxygen species (ROS) from CTE excited states for their use in photodynamic therapy, might also be possible. A previously described CTE carvone-based polymer was used to explore this idea. The results show that not only is it possible to transfer the excess energy from the long-lived excited states to molecular oxygen to produce singlet oxygen (one of the most relevant ROS), but more importantly, under violet light irradiation, over 99.9% of *Staphylococcus aureus* cells are eradicated using fluences comparable to those used in traditional systems. Uncovering these photophysical properties of CTE opens the door to a revolutionary breakthrough that promises to disrupt conventional photodynamic therapy and usher in a new era of CTE-based photosensitisers.

1. Introduction

Health has been a crucial aspect of human progress since ancient times. Serious diseases, particularly infectious ones, can lead to pandemic scenarios that significantly impact human civilisation's economic, political, and social aspects.[1] In a world with an ageing and infection-prone population, tackling infectious diseases and the hurdle of antimicrobial resistance is imperative.[2] That's why, in 2017, the World Health Organization (WHO) published its first list of 'priority pathogens' for antibiotic research and development.[3] The aim is to develop new antimicrobial agents that effectively combat infections while minimising resistance to them.[4,5]

In this battle, photodynamic therapy (PDT) has been proposed as an alternative therapy to overcome antibiotic resistance. PDT is a non-invasive form of phototherapy [6,7] that uses harmless light to activate non or low-toxic photosensitive chemicals, known as photosensitizers (PS), to generate cytotoxic oxidant Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) by energy or electron transfer from a long-lived excited state.[8] PDT has a multitarget mode of action for eradicating malignant cells, derived from the broad reactivity of ROS against a wide range of cell components (i.e. lipids, DNA, proteins or carbohydrates), which hinders the emergence of bacterial resistance, making PDT an ideal alternative to conventional antibacterial treatment.[9,10] However, the photosensitizing ability of traditional PSs is severely inhibited by aggregation-induced quenching (ACQ) after PS accumulation at bacteria, leading to minor ROS production.[11]

Therefore, if aggregation causes an efficiency penalty, Aggregated Induced Emission (AIE) appears as the solution to overcome this problem. Upon aggregation, AIE materials' (AIEgens) emissive and photosensitizing properties are enhanced.[12-14] In fact, these materials could be rationally designed to undergo aggregation under specific physiological conditions of the bacterial cell, increasing the efficiency and the selectivity of the PDT treatment.[15-19] Although there have been some studies of AIEgens with great potential for future preclinical and clinical translation (especially as photoanticancer agents),[20,21] their structure, based on a conjugated (aromatic) system, is usually associated with low stability, mutagenicity, and biocompatibility.[22,23] In this context, several independent laboratories have reported the emission from non-conjugated

unconventional chromophores such as polyamides, dendrimers or aminoacids.[24-26] The phenomenon is explained in terms of Clustering-Triggered Emission (CTE), where the aggregation of heteroatoms (N, O, S and P) and/or unsaturated bonds (C=O, C=C and C≡N) leads to the formation of emissive clusters,[27-29] due to the intramolecular through-space interaction (TSI) between the n and π electrons close in proximity.[30-32] This concept disrupts the traditional luminescence paradigm by attributing light absorption and emission to the different clouds of electrons resulting from a cluster formed by intra- and/or inter-interaction in the system [27,29] rather than the typical electron conjugation through bonds. Hence, the considerable amount of research proving the similarity between excited states CTE and those of traditional chromophores and/or quantum dots suggests the possibility of additional phenomena occurring,[33] and it is not too much of a stretch to think that some CTEgens materials could generate long-lived excited states capable of generating ROS.

To validate this hypothesis, a CTE system, specifically a carvone-based biomass polymer, was selected in this study. The results are a significant milestone in the production of PSs, as they provide the first conclusive evidence that CTE excited states can contribute to the generation of ROS. The principle has not only been validated spectroscopically but it has also been used as a photo antimicrobial agent against Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* bacteria. Finally, the results undoubtedly demonstrated that while this carvone-based polymer is not toxic in the absence of light, its photoantimicrobial effect on the bacteria is significantly enhanced. It is clear, therefore, that CTEgens can undertake processes previously thought to be the exclusive domain of traditional chromophores, suggesting that applications previously limited to those chromophores, such as photosensitisation, could now be developed using CTEgens.

2. Results and discussion

2.1 Synthesis

The synthesis of the polymer was developed according to a previously reported procedure (Figure 1).^[26] It should be noted that the reagents (carvone and phthalic anhydride) and solvents (toluene and dichloromethane) used in the synthesis process were sublimated and/or distilled on more than three occasions to ensure their purity. However, it is of the utmost importance to identify the presence of any impurity, even at the trace level, in CTE systems, as any such impurity may affect the photophysical properties of these systems, consequently, their luminescence mechanism.^[29,34] Therefore, a highly sensitive method based on liquid chromatography–high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC–HRMS) was employed for this purpose. Figure S1 shows the comparison between the TICs for the polymer mixture and the blank control samples. Peaks between 13 and 19 minutes in the LC run were assigned to oligo(PA-alt-COExo)-related species; data from table S1 shows the gradual incorporation of (PA-COExo) units to COExo, starting with one unit (m/z 521.2177) and reaching up to seven units (m/z 2405.9100) (Figure S2). Molecular ions in the detected peaks were a mixture of proton ($M+H^+$) and sodium ($M+Na^+$) adducts, with the latter being the most abundant one. Being the foundation upon which the higher-level oligomers were built, the structures of COExo-(PA-COExo)₁ and COExo-(PA-COExo)₂ were studied in detail through MS/MS experiments (figure S3), with the proposed structures for the observed fragments shown in table S2 and confirming the identity of the associated species. Since no COExo peak was observed in the TIC, and the rest of the peaks were related to these oligomeric structures with no presence of extraneous species, the LC-MS analysis provided strong evidence that the source of the observed light-interacting mechanism (absorption, emission, or other relaxation processes), are the oligo(PA-alt-COExo)-related species.

Figure 1. Synthesis of poly(PA-*alt*-COExo) according to reference.[26] DMAP = 4-dimethylaminopyridine.

2.2. Photophysical and Photochemical Properties

A dilute solution of carvone polymer in tetrahydrofuran (THF, a good solvent) appears colourless to the naked eye, showing neither absorption nor emission. However, when the concentration of the polymer is increased to over 0.1 g/L, the UV absorption undergoes a subtle change, exhibiting a tail extending into the visible region and becoming emissive in the blue/green region of the spectrum (Figure 2A). As previously reported, the phenomenon observed for this polymer is ascribed to the n,π^* and π,π^* electronic transitions that arise from the formation of different clouds of electrons of the through-space interaction generated clusters,^[26] and is exacerbated by the presence of water (Figure 2B). When the water content exceeds 50% of v/v, the polymer starts to aggregate, changing the structure of the cluster. Under these conditions, a turbid suspension with a much brighter emission is obtained due to the more crowded structure of the aggregated polymer compared to neat THF (Figure 2C).

Figure 2. Absorption (red solid lines) and emission (blue dashed lines; $\lambda_{\text{Exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$) spectra of the polymer in THF (A), H₂O (B) and THF:H₂O mixtures (C).

One question that can be addressed is whether these excited clusters can interact with oxygen to produce ROS. One of the simplest methods for investigating this phenomenon is to monitor the production of singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) by recording its weak NIR phosphorescence at 1275 nm (see Figure S4 for a detailed NIR spectral analysis).^[35,36] Figure 3 shows the typical time-resolved emission of $^1\text{O}_2$ after nanosecond pulsed excitation of the polymer in THF and in H_2O (panels A,B respectively), where the $^1\text{O}_2$ production increases non-linearly with the polymer concentration (Figure S5). This process is highly efficient, as evidenced by the high $^1\text{O}_2$ production quantum yield ($\Phi_\Delta = 0.45$; Figure S6), comparable to well-established clinically used PSs.^[37,38] It is also noteworthy that this pathway is an order of magnitude more favourable than the emission of a photon by the cluster ($\Phi_f < 2 \cdot 10^{-2}$), highlighting the significant preference of this CTEgen material for the generation of long-lived excited states capable of generating ROS.

The time-resolved $^1\text{O}_2$ phosphorescence signals provide additional insight into the formation and fate of this ROS. In THF, the kinetic traces of $^1\text{O}_2$ show rise and decay lifetimes of 0.3 and 20 μs , assigned to the lifetimes of the $^1\text{O}_2$ precursor, namely the triplet state of the cluster (τ_T), and of $^1\text{O}_2$ (τ_Δ), respectively (Figure 3A). Indeed, the long-lived CTE excited state formation was confirmed by transient absorption experiments in which the ground-state cluster absorption recovers within a lifetime of 40 μs in deoxygenated samples and 0.3 μs in air-saturated solutions (Figure 3A inset; Figure S7). Two main observations can be made from here: a) the τ_T is slightly longer than established conventional photosensitizers (typically around τ_T of 0.2 μs)^[39] with a bimolecular quenching rate larger than $1 \times 10^9 \text{ M}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ (Figure S7), and b) the τ_Δ rises upon increasing the polymer concentration (Figure S8). The initial observation is related to the fact that the oxygen accessibility to the cluster is slightly hindered, as well as the occurrence of both dynamic and static quenching, as evidenced by the non-linearity of the Stern-Volmer plot. The latter may be attributed to the preferential diffusion of the generated $^1\text{O}_2$ can preferentially diffuse along the polymer chain before its escape from the polymer matrix. These two effects become more apparent when the polymer structure collapses and forms aggregates upon increasing the water concentration.

Figure 3. Singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) phosphorescence kinetic traces of the polymer in THF (A) and H_2O (B), where the polymer concentration range was varied from 0 to 0.5 g/L in panels A,B. The insets in both figures depict the transient absorption traces of ground state bleaching recovery ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{obs}} = 380 \text{ nm}$) at a polymer concentration of 0.5 g/L. Comparison of $^1\text{O}_2$ (t_T (E) and t_Δ (F)) with increasing the water content in the THF: H_2O solvent mixtures.

To verify this hypothesis, the kinetics of the polymer in different THF: H_2O (v/v) mixtures were measured (Figure 3C,D). At low water concentration, τ_Δ decreases with increasing the water content, as expected from the shorter τ_Δ in neat water than in neat THF ($\tau_{\Delta,\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 3.3 \mu\text{s}$; $\tau_{\Delta,\text{THF}} = 20 \mu\text{s}$).^[39] However, this observation is reverted (i.e., τ_Δ increases), when the water content exceeds a certain threshold. This fact is consistent with the observation that water induces polymer aggregation and, consequently, a stronger and more tightly-packed clusterization.^[26] It is, therefore, not surprising that the kinetic profile of $^1\text{O}_2$ is altered, with both lifetimes being enlarged (Figure 3E,F). Tight packing in the clusters hinders the diffusion of O_2 into the cluster and the escape of $^1\text{O}_2$ into the external aqueous environment. Thus, the decay rate of the cluster's

excited state is reduced, as evidenced by the slower ground state bleaching recovery of the cluster observed after laser flash photolysis in air-saturated water (Figure 3B inset), and the decay of $^1\text{O}_2$ is also slowed down due to the fact $^1\text{O}_2$ diffusion within the polymer becomes the rate-determining step. This is confirmed by the slight variation τ_{Δ} upon deuteration of the aqueous phase (from 105 to 115 μs in H_2O and D_2O , respectively; Figure S9), while τ_{Δ} in neat H_2O and D_2O are 3.3 and 68 μs , respectively.[40] Indeed, under this condition, the $^1\text{O}_2$ kinetic trace still obeys a monoexponential rise and decay profile, suggesting that a fast chemical equilibrium is achieved between the $^1\text{O}_2$ located inside and outside the polymer microenvironment.[41] Accordingly, in consideration of the kinetic model for $^1\text{O}_2$ decay in a heterogeneous medium developed by Rodgers et al.,[41] only a tiny fraction of $^1\text{O}_2$ (less than 3% of the total) is capable of escaping from the polymer matrix and entering the external aqueous phase (Figure 4; further details can be found in Figure S9/Table S3). Although this fraction is small, the $^1\text{O}_2$ escaping molecules can still be trapped by a $^1\text{O}_2$ -selective fluorescent probe located at the aqueous phase and/or absorbed at the surface of the polymer phase, such as tryptophan (Figure S10). Therefore, these $^1\text{O}_2$ escaping molecules will be the cytotoxic species responsible for the (photo)-antimicrobial activity (vide infra).

Figure 4. Description of the heterogeneous polymer suspension in water. Schematic description of the polymer and aqueous phases, including all the steps, in which the formation and decay of $^1\text{O}_2$ is involved. Legend: C: cluster, ET: Energy transfer, S: substrate, and S- O_2 : Oxidized substrate.

To get a more complete picture, the effect of polymer concentration on the CTE photophysics/photochemistry has been explored (Figures 2,3). As a starting point, the properties were studied in THF. While no absorption, fluorescence, or $^1\text{O}_2$ production could be observed at low polymer concentration (< 0.1 g/L), non-linear enhancements were recorded upon increasing the polymer concentration. This phenomenon has previously been observed for AIEgens PSs, whereby the aggregation of the PS favours the population of both singlet and triplet excited states.[25-29] Even though it is not unprecedented for CTE processes to be interpreted in terms of AIEgens, a concentration-dependent behaviour in the formation of singlet and triplet excited states should be observed to validate such mechanism. As shown in Figure S11, the absorption, fluorescence, and $^1\text{O}_2$ production increase non-linearly with the polymer concentration in both solvents. Moreover, higher polymer concentration leads to a lengthening of τ_T due to the formation of a dense polymer cluster network, which is less permeable to molecular oxygen,[42] and longer τ_Δ can be attributed to the decrease in the density of $^1\text{O}_2$ quenching sites along the polymer aggregates compared to neat water.[43] These results not only support a mechanism similar to that observed for AIEgens, but also strongly support the potential of this polymer to form cluster aggregates, where their long-lived excited states that can transfer their energy to molecular oxygen to generate significant amounts of $^1\text{O}_2$.

2.3 Photodynamic inactivation of bacteria

Encouraged by the observed production of $^1\text{O}_2$, the photoantimicrobial capabilities of this polymer were evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus* ATCC 29213). This species, a representative example of Gram-positive bacteria, was chosen as a pathogenic model to unravel the potential application of CTEgens materials for photoantimicrobial treatments.[44] To perform this experiment, the bacterial cell suspensions were incubated with the polymer in the dark at 37 °C for 30 minutes. After the incubation period, the suspension was divided into two fractions, one kept in the dark to assess the intrinsic toxicity of the polymer and one irradiated with violet light (400 nm, 15 mW/cm²; Figure S12). The irradiated sample showed strong concentration-dependent photoantimicrobial activity at the two light fluences tested (27 and 80 J/cm²) in a concentration-dependent manner (Figure 5A), whereas the polymer did not induce any dark toxicity, even at the highest concentration tested. Specifically, a remarkable viability reduction of 6 log₁₀ colony forming units (CFU) reduction (99.9999%) was achieved at a concentration of 150 µg/mL (80 J/cm²), whereas a reduction of at least ≥3 log₁₀CFU reduction (99.9%), already considered biologically relevant in hand hygiene guidelines,[45] was observed under milder conditions. It is noteworthy that violet light is slightly phototoxic (approximately 1 log₁₀CFU reduction) for *S. aureus* at the highest fluence tested, in accordance with the current literature on blue light PDI.[46,47] This fact complicates the selection of a UV light source with a better spectral overlap with the absorption of the polymer, which should be considered in the next generation of CTEgens materials for PDT.

To identify the origin of the phototoxicity, the photoinactivation was repeated using the same bacteria suspended in deuterated phosphate buffer (d-PBS), which lengthens τ_{Δ} and therefore its photooxidative toxicity.[40,48] In this case, the light-induced toxicity increased for both cases (in the absence or presence of polymer; Figure 5B). However, a significantly larger increase is observed in the presence of the polymer ($p < 0.0001$; Figure S13), indicating that $^1\text{O}_2$ plays a key role in the photoinactivation of *S. aureus* by a CTEgen in agreement with the abovementioned spectroscopic results. Although these positive results motivated us to test the photoantimicrobial

activity in two other pathogenic models of Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* ATCC 35218 and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 27853),^[49] no significant photoinactivation was observed (Figure S14). The most likely reason for this is that these bacteria have a more complex cell wall and the lack of electrostatic affinity of the negative bacterial surface.^[50]

Figure 5. (Photo)-antimicrobial response of the polymer irradiated with violet light (400 nm). (A): Survival curves of *Staphylococcus aureus* with different concentrations of polymer and irradiated with increasing violet light fluences (black, red, and blue lines for 0, 27 and 80 J/cm^2 , respectively). (B): Mechanistic studies of the photo-antimicrobial response in which *S. aureus* bacterial cells have been resuspended in PBS (red) or D-PBS (blue) in the absence (dark) or presence (light) of 0.15 g/L of polymer. The photodynamic treatment fluence is 27 J/cm^2 .

3. Conclusion

This work represents a turning point in the development of the next generation of PSs, as it is the first report to demonstrate that light excitation of CTEgen materials, such as this carvone-based polymer, can trigger long-lived excited states that could efficiently transfer their excess energy to molecular oxygen to produce ROS such as $^1\text{O}_2$. The novel mechanism outlined shows that CTEgens, together with their previously identified unique intrinsic luminescence, function in every respect as the well-described traditional chromophores. Furthermore, the demonstration of their high photoantimicrobial activity against a Gram-positive pathogenic bacterial model such as *S. aureus* laid the foundation for the generation of a new family of photosensitizers based on CTEgen materials. Most importantly, CTE phenomena have been detected and described in various polymers approved by the FDA/EMA as excipients, drug delivery vehicles or food additives, so that in vitro CTE-based PDT treatments should have an accelerated translation to preclinical and clinical phases, thereby reducing the economic cost of the overall process by eliminating several regulatory steps.^[51,52] Taken together, these provide an excellent starting point for CTE-based PDT to address the current limitations of PDT, with the aim of ensuring long-term, effective healthcare with the most sustainable system possible.

4. Methods

4.1 Synthesis of poly(PA-alt-COExo)

In the glovebox, toluene (5 mL), 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (31 mg, 254.5 μmol), carvone-based epoxide (COExo) (846 mg, 5.09 mmol) and phthalic anhydride (PA) (754 mg, 5.09 mmol) were placed into a 10 mL Schlenk equipped with a small stir bar. The Schlenk was then taken out of the glovebox and placed in a preheated oil bath under a nitrogen atmosphere at 95 °C for 24 h. Once the polyester was obtained, the viscous mixture was dissolved in the minimum amount of dichloromethane, precipitated with an excess of methanol and, finally, filtered off and dried to constant weight to afford a white solid (1.47 g, 92%).

4.2 Characterization of Purity of poly(PA-alt-COExo)

After appropriate dilution of the solid (1.12 mg of purified solid was dissolved in 3 mL 1:1:1 (v/v/v) H₂O:MeOH:THF), Liquid chromatography coupled to high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) was employed for the analysis of artifacts and impurities. A UHPLC-Q-Orbitrap-MS/MS analysis was conducted utilising a Vanquish™ UHPLC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Carlsbad, CA, USA) connected to a Q-Exactive mass spectrometer (Thermo Scientific) with heated electrospray ionisation. The separation was conducted on a Zorbax Eclipse plus-C18 Rapid column (2.1 mm x 150 mm, 1.8 μm) (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, MA, USA). The mobile phase consisted of water (A) and methanol (B), both of which had 0.1% formic acid. A flow rate of 0.3 mL min⁻¹ was selected, with a gradient starting at 10% B, then linearly increasing to 95% B at 17.0 min; remaining constant at 95% B until 5.0 min; decreasing to 10% B at 20.0 min; and being maintained constant for re-equilibration. The column was maintained at a temperature of 30 °C, and the injection volume was 1 μL .

The mass spectrum data was acquired in both positive and negative ion mode through full MS and higher energy collisional dissociation (HCD) data-dependent MS/MS by the UHPLC-Q-Orbitrap-MS/MS, which was equipped with a control software (Xcalibur, version 4.2.27). The scan parameters were set as follows: mass-to-charge ratio (m/z) scan range, 170 to 2500 Da; resolution, 70,000; automatic gain control (AGC) target, 3×10^6 ; maximum injection time, 100 ms. The following parameters were employed for the heated electrospray ionisation source (HESI

source): spray voltage, 3.0 kV for ESI⁻ and 3.5 kV for ESI⁺; sheath gas flow rate, 40 arb; auxiliary gas flow rate, 10 arb; sweep gas flow rate, 0 arb; capillary temperature, 320 °C; s-lens RF level, 50; and auxiliary gas heater temperature, 350 °C. A data-dependent scan (dd-MS2) was employed to obtain high-quality MS2 data. The five most intense precursors were automatically selected for MS/MS fragmentation by HCD. The parameters of the dd-MS2 method were as follows: resolution, 17,500; AGC target, 2×10^5 ; maximum IT, 100 ms; loop count, 5; isolation window, 1 m/z. The Normalised Collision Energy (NCE) was set at 15 and 30 V.

4.3 Photophysical and photochemical characterization

All the solvents used for the photophysical, and photochemical characterization have spectroscopic grade or MiliQ water. UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded using a Varian Cary 6000i spectrometer (Varian, Palo Alto, CA, USA). Fluorescence emission spectra were recorded using a Spex Fluoromax-4 spectrofluorometer (Horiba Jobin-Yvon, Edison, NJ, USA).

¹O₂ generation was studied by time-resolved near-infrared phosphorescence using a customised Fluotime 200 time-resolved spectrophotometer (PicoQuant, Berlin, Germany).[35,36] A diode-pumped Nd:YAG laser (FTSS355-Q, Crystal Laser, Berlin, Germany) working at a 1-kHz repetition rate (0.5 μJ per pulse) was used for excitation at 355 nm. A 1064 nm rugate notch filter (Edmund Optics) and an uncoated SKG-5 filter (CVI Laser Corporation) were placed in the laser path to remove any residual NIR emission. The ¹O₂ phosphorescence emitted by the sample was filtered with a 1100 nm long-pass filter (Edmund Optics) and later by a narrow bandpass filter at 1275 nm (BK-1270-70-B, bk Interferenzoptik). A thermoelectric-cooled NIR-sensitive photomultiplier tube assembly (H10330C-45-C3, Hamamatsu Photonics, Hamamatsu, Japan) was used as detector. Photon counting was achieved with a multichannel scaler (NanoHarp 250, PicoQuant, Berlin, Germany). The time dependence of the ¹O₂ phosphorescence with the signal intensity S(t) is described by Equation 1, in which τ_T and τ_Δ are the lifetimes of the photosensitizer triplet state and of ¹O₂ respectively, and S(0) is a preexponential parameter proportional to the ¹O₂ formation quantum yield (Φ_Δ). For the methodology for determining Φ_Δ , please check Figure S4. The used reference photosensitizer is phenalenone ($\Phi_\Delta = 1$).[53-55]

$$S(t) = S(0) \times \left(\frac{\tau_{\Delta}}{\tau_{\Delta} - \tau_T} \right) \times (e^{-t/\tau_{\Delta}} - e^{-t/\tau_T}) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Transient absorption kinetics (ΔAbs) were acquired using a home-built nanosecond laser flash photolysis system.^[56] Briefly, the sample was excited by a 355 nm Q-switched Nd:YAG Laser (Surelite I-10, Continuum) with right-angle geometry. The analysing beam is composed by a Xe lamp (PTI, 75 W) in combination with a dual-grating monochromator (mod. 101, PTI) coupled to a UV-Vis radiation detector (PTI 710). The observation wavelength was selected to 380 nm which corresponds to the ground state bleaching of the generated molecular clusters. The signal was fed to a Lecroy WaveSurfer 454 oscilloscope for digitizing and averaging (10 shots) and finally transferred to a PC for data storage and analysis.

4.4 Photoantimicrobial studies

Three different strains, one gram-positive, *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*, ATCC 29213) and two gram-negative, *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*, ATCC 35218) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*, ATCC 27853) were used in this study. Briefly, the culture media used for growing the cells was Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB). The PDT treatment protocol was adapted from Ref.^[57]. The strains were grown overnight at 37 ± 1 °C in an orbital shaker at 60 rpm under aerobic conditions. Then, 100 μL of the culture were grown in 10 mL of fresh TSB until reaching an optical density of 0.18, measured at 600 nm. These OD_{600} values corresponds to bacterial concentration of 10^7 CFU/mL for *S. aureus*, and 10^8 CFU/mL for *E. coli* and *P. aeruginosa*. After that, bacteria were harvested by centrifugation (4000 rpm, 10 min) and resuspended in the same volume of sterile PBS or deuterated-PBS. Then, the adequate concentration of the polymer dissolved in DMSO (always $\leq 1\%$) was added to the bacterial suspension and let incubate for 60 minutes in dark conditions. After, the bacterial suspension was irradiated using a violet LED (Figure S9) until reach the adequate light fluence (15.2 mW/cm^2). 1 mL of the bacterial suspension was kept unirradiated and used as dark control. After the PDT treatment, the bacterial suspensions were diluted by a factor of 10, until reaching a 10^{-6} dilution factor. Finally, 10 μL of every dilution were spread on

Tryptic Soy Agar and were incubated aerobically at 37 ± 1 °C. The colony forming units (CFU) were counted after 24 hours of incubation and the dilution factor was considered.

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Author contributions

C.M. and R.B.-O. conceived the research and initiated the project. F. de la C.-M., A.L.-S. and J.A.C.O. synthesized and purified the polymer. J.F.G.-R. assessed the purity of the polymer. K.D., R.B.-O. and S.N. performed the photophysical and photochemical characterization and processed the data. K.D., O.G., and M.A. performed the photoantimicrobial studies. C.M. and R.B.-O. prepared the manuscript and all the other authors contributed to the manuscript. C.M., S.N., and R.B.-O. supervised the project.

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